

METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Axmadaliyeva Dildora Farhodjon qizi.

dildoraahmadaliyeva339@gmail.com

4th yea student of English Language and Literature

Faculty of Fergana State University.

Karimova Shohista Zohidjon qizi

4th yea student of English Language and Literature

Faculty of Fergana State University.

ANNOTATION

This article highlights different methods used in foreign languages and ways of achieving this goal. It is employed to determine how to provide learners with learning resources of varying scales.

KEY WORDS

Foreign language, methods, form of teaching, interactive method, methodology, education .

Teaching methods are the broader techniques used to achieve student learning outcomes, while activities are different ways of applying those methods. Learning methods help students; acquire course content, learn how to use the content in a specific context. There are a lot of methods in foreign languages, for example, grammar translation method, text translation method ,explicit method ,direct method ,translation method and other.

The method of translation. "Translation methods" is another phrase that is sometimes used interchangeably with the name of this procedure. It is not challenging to understand what the name means: foreign linguistic resources are translated into the

original vocabulary. Translation was initially utilized throughout Europe. as a means of comprehending Greek, and afterwards Spanish. In the latter part of the 18th century, Between the 18th and 19th centuries, French was studied, and during the 1920s, English and German was ultimately studied through conversion. Among Muslims, Arabic and Foreign languages were studied, including Persian. Living and dead languages, like Latin, were translated information, a procedure that was thought to have played a role in the creation of rational thought. Alternatively, Arabic was a way to instruct in Islamic

Grammar translation method is a way of teaching in which students study grammar and translate words into their own language. Richards and Rodgers claim that grammatical problems constituted the main focus of the mid-1800s. To clarify the language's grammatical norms, they provided examples of constructions. Authors from this era were primarily concerned in organizing the morphology and syntax of L2. There weren't many written or oral exercises. The most common author of this era is most likely Karl Plötz. The only way to learn in his textbooks was through translation. Plötz frequently employed the phrases "Thou hast a book," which Titone cited. The home is exquisite. He owns a good dog. There is bread [sic]. Titone (1968), page 27 Richards and Rodgers (1986), page 3.

Direct method. In response to the grammar-translation method, the direct method—also referred to as the natural approach—was developed. The spoken language is highlighted here. This method focuses on hearing and comprehension in the early stages of language learning, drawing on observations of young toddlers acquiring their mother tongues. The target language is used to teach lessons; speaking in one's own tongue is actually severely prohibited. In a typical class, students would first see graphics while the teacher goes over the vocabulary words, and then they would listen to recordings of these words being used in understandable language. Since grammar teaching isn't given directly, speaking is encouraged at all times once pupils have had time to listen to and process the sounds of the target language. Instead, grammar should be taught to students inductively. Give them permission.

Explicit method

With little left for students to figure out on their own, explicit teaching is a teacher-centered approach that emphasizes explaining what has to be done and how to do it. To clearly define what is expected of students in order for them to achieve, teachers establish and communicate explicit learning objectives and associated success criteria (Victorian Government, 2022).

Furthermore, teachers employ modeling to guide students through new material and regularly assess their comprehension before concluding each class with a summary that ties the whole learning process together (Victorian Government, 2022). To help students acquire mastery, teachers should design lessons that progress in complexity step by step and give them opportunities to practice what they have learned.

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